

COMPUTER NETWORKS AND LEARNING FROM THEM OPPORTUNITIES TO USE

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Annotation: In this article, it is written about computer networks and their classification, organization of information transfer process.

Key words: computer system, information, computing techniques, electrical signals.

Description and classification of computer system as you know, there are many types of computers today there are types and they are experienced in all areas. But that's it in this regard, a question arises: Different computers are practically the same whether it is necessary to receive power in different ways or according to their power and type Is it best to use it in different ways? Among these methods what boot states can be accessed? Such an organization or firm how to improve and how to help when using methods do you think it will come? Modern production processes process data at great speed production with, its convenient storage and power requirement does. In addition, you can quickly search for information and find it for this to require mathematical and logical processing the participation of the majority and the demand for assembly. The process of making management decisions is the production of these decisions requires the direct participation of all parties in the exit process. Centralized planning of computing techniques treatment of all problems with the same efficiency they preferred to have portable computers. But visual inspection of issues to be resolved with the matching of the power of such computers brought forward much of the expenditure. This kind of universal centralized search of computer resources It became very complicated due to the help of the method. Because everyone is the same the resources received by several users at the same time to refer to disagreements (conflicts) between them would issue. Centralized information production information increase in the production process provision could not fully meet the requirements of the system provided several production aids and dialog information hindered the organization of production in a

convenient way. for example great for the main system of the computer short work would cause inconvenience, because of the resulting system most connected computers are completely or partially disabled were released. This situation required a lot of effort and work.

In the second example, several computers belong to one region located in different places and they start the data they transfer the obtained results to the central computer. The complex organized in this way is remote we can call it a multi-machine computing complex. Different from these as a computer network communication channels and additional special and computers connected to each other through devices refers to a system or complex of terminals that transmit information in a distributed manner should be adapted to production requirements. Here is the system or a set of computers, their peripherals, software supply, related technical support, and the person managing the system resources are understood and the process of their joint production of information and providing operational communication with other systems should be given. Computer networks are the ultimate multi-machine system is the stage of development, the main of their multi-machine complexes the difference is:

*There are several multi-machine computing complexes if it consists only of computers, there are several computer networks consists of dozens or hundreds of computers and their the distance between them can be hundreds or thousands of kilometers;

* Information production in multi-machine computing complexes, transfer it and manage the system on one or more computers if increased, in computer networks this work is a number in the network distributed among computers;

* Data communication channels from one computer to another with different ways (routes) depending on the situation In the second example, several computers belong to one region located in different places and they start the data they transfer the obtained results to the central computer.

The station was engaged in data transmission and storage hardware is understood. Subscribers and stations are often subscribers system, to organize their interaction it is required to have a physical media that transmits data. Information transmitting physical medium is the communication channel or space through which electrical signals are propagated it can. Information between subscriber systems using this environment establish a communication network that provides exchange will be done. So, any network subscriber systems and communication can be viewed as a set of networks. Classification (classification)

of computing networks It depends on the territorial location of the subscriber's systems we can divide computing networks into the following three groups:

- * Global networks (WAN- Wide Area Network)
- * Regional networks (MAN - Metropolitan Area Network)
- * Local networks (LAN- Local Area Network)

Global networks in different countries and continents serves to connect the subscribers located with each other. In this case, communication between subscribers is through telephone channels, radio communication can be carried out through or through satellites. Such a global networks all information resources on a human scale when combined, makes it possible to use them effectively.

Regional networks are located at long distances from each other, but communication between subscribers belonging to a single territory is carried out serves to increase. They are large city subscribers, economical may include a territory or a separate country. Such the distance between subscribers in the network is several tens or hundreds can be kilometers. Local networks connect subscribers located in a small area and implements their interaction. An example as computing networks of enterprises, firms or banks can be brought. If the above three different networks are combined, hierarchical multi-branched structures are formed. So complicated Visible networks are large-scale and diverse data allows to use resources and process them.

An example of such a network is the Internet we can bring. Its composition is very numerous and diverse type includes interconnected networks. Each concrete the user can use it for their own purposes and it is necessary he will be able to get the information no matter where he is. Network structure for the user, methods of information exchange application and data are not important. Whatever personal computers, which are an integral element of the management system with the emergence and wide spread of local computing networks developed with Because private computers are on the network In practice, working together leads to greater efficiency confirmed.

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